

ISic1168

I.Sicily inscription 1168

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

sandstone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Thermae Himeraeae

Place of origin (modern)

Termini Imerese

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Palermo, Museo Archeologico

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. Μηβία Μάξιμα

2. έπεδήμησεν

3. έτη ξε

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 491456

EDR 135972

EDCS 41400013

EDCS 39102324

PHI 140653

PHI 175720

PHI 330047

Bibliography

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